

IMPORTANCE OF PERENNIAL WHEAT IN IMPROVING SOIL STRUCTURE AND OBTAINING GREEN MASS

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Abstract: Using traditional breeding methods, perennial wheat varieties have been created that combine the characteristics of annual wheat. The peculiarity of these varieties is that after the wheat crop is harvested, wheat grows again from the root mass and can be used for a second harvest or as pasture for livestock. Perennial wheat varieties allow to further improve the condition of eroded and degraded soils, which have become a problem for a long time, and make it possible to make rational use of unproductive lands.

Key words: wheat, erosion, degradation, soil, green mass, selection, root, variety, crop, disease.

The increase in the number of people in the world leads to an increase in the demand for food products. About 47 percent of the irrigated arable land in our republic consists of soils with various levels of salinity and degradation. In the last few decades, one third of the total arable land in the world has suffered soil erosion [4,5]. Fertile irrigated lands are widely used for growing annual crops. Barren lands prone to salinity and close to seepage are becoming unfit for cultivation. Perennial wheat varieties allow to further improve the condition of the eroded and degraded soils, which have become a problem for a long time, and make it possible to use the unproductive lands wisely [6].

The first scientific research work on the creation of perennial wheat began in 1928 in Russia by Academician N.V. Sitsin, who in his experiments used soft wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) with perennial grasses (*Agropyron glaucium*) (by crossing with *A. elongatum*) in 1937 created the first sources K-23086 and K-34035, which combined characteristics of perennial wheat [3].

Perennial wheat is considered a new type of crop, scientific research institutes of developed countries and international scientific centers are conducting scientific research on the creation and introduction of their new varieties. The use of perennial wheat varieties as a food and fodder crop allows further development of grain and animal husbandry. One of the main features of perennial wheat is the prevention of soil erosion, the organic residue of the root mass enriches the soil, and the high coefficient of use of water and nutrients [1].

Global climate change makes scientific research on perennial wheat even more important. Because this type of crop is resistant to various factors of nature, heat, drought, salinity and diseases, it is possible to harvest for several years with one planting. Experiments show that replanting works are carried out again after 3-5 years in the area planted with perennial wheat. In the experiments, 1,500 tons of blue pulp per hectare were obtained from the first harvest of perennial wheat. It was harvested three times until late autumn. It was found that it has the ability to accumulate up to 4.2 tons of green mass during the season, and through this green mass, it can collect enough feed for 150 sheep. This saves a lot of resources and money in production [2].

In recent years, in cooperation with The International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center (known by its Spanish acronym, CIMMYT) and the Land Science Research Institute of the State of Kansas, the United States of America, many experiments have been conducted on the creation and introduction of new varieties of perennial wheat in progress. Different from the perennial forms used in Russia, perennial grasses *Th. intermedium*, *Th. junceiforme* and *Th. ponticum* belonging to the sedge family were used as donors in the experiments. Currently, perennial forms with 42 chromosomes have been created, the main disadvantages of which are 30-60% of yield, 15-25% of weight of 1000 pieces, and 10-15% of protein and gluten indicators. Therefore, in order to further improve the valuable indicators of these samples, it is necessary to cross them with local varieties [5].

Since 2017, more than 10 samples of perennial wheat have been planted at the Scientific Research Institute of Plant Genetic Resources (Plant Science) and preliminary testing has been started. In the project, on the basis of crossbreeding of perennial forms of wheat with locally regionalized annual forms, heat, drought, disease-resistant, high root mass, vigorous growing in infertile lands, suitable for use as grain and fodder the main goal is to create and introduce wheat varieties into production. Currently, the project is being carried out in cooperation with the scientists of the Scientific Research Institute of Plant Genetic Resources, the Gallaorol Lalmi Agriculture Scientific Research Institute and the International Scientific Center of CIMMYT. Most importantly, the main issue in the creation of these varieties is planting in degraded gypsum lands and improving the soil structure of these lands, planting in mountain and sub-mountain regions, forestry and lower regions, and replanting from June to October it is intended to be used as green fodder for livestock.

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